

Spatial patterns in the tumor microenvironment identify therapy response in breast cancer using weakly supervised learning

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Abstract

The tumor microenvironment (TME) influences treatment response in breast cancer, yet identifying spatial patterns predictive of treatment response remains a challenge. Here we applied cyclic immunofluorescence proteomics to phenotype approximately 5.5×10^5 single cells from pre-treatment tissue biopsies of 13 ER-positive breast cancer patients. For each cancer cell, a radial distribution-based neighborhood was constructed by calculating the distribution of identified phenotypes up to a radius of 200 μm , resulting in a total of 2.0×10^5 neighborhoods. To identify responder-associated neighborhood patterns, an ensemble of neural networks combining autoencoding and multiple-instance learning was trained on sample-level response labels to neoadjuvant chemotherapy with bevacizumab. The resulting model distinguished responders from non-responders in cross-validation, ranked held-out responders above non-responders, and revealed spatially heterogeneous responder-like areas within tumors. These findings demonstrate that weakly supervised learning of spatial proteomic data can identify clinically relevant TME structures associated with treatment response.

Keywords: Tumor microenvironment, Breast cancer, Spatial proteomics, Multiple-instance learning, Neoadjuvant chemotherapy, Spatial biomarker

Introduction

The tumor microenvironment (TME) plays an important role in breast cancer. Interactions between cancer cells and their neighbors can shape disease progression and treatment response. Examples of the TME influencing treatment response have been shown with

macrophage density reducing the efficacy of chemotherapy or cancer-associated fibroblasts mediating resistance to neoadjuvant therapy (Desgres et al., 2025; Salvagno et al., 2019; Shree et al., 2011). Furthermore, TME properties may affect both short- and long-term clinical outcomes (Azimzade et al., 2026)). While the TME can impact cancer cells, studies have also found that intrinsic cancer mutations can shape the TME. One such example is mutation in BRCA1 that sensitizes cancer cells to platinum-based chemotherapy by impairing homologous recombination, which in turn induces distinct TME changes (Danenberg et al., 2022).

These examples illustrate how the TME structure contains clinically relevant information that can inform our understanding of cancer behavior and treatment outcomes. Multiplexed imaging studies have demonstrated that breast tumors contain recurrent TME structures associated with molecular subtype, genomic features and clinical outcome (Danenberg et al., 2022). Spatial features of the TME have also been linked directly to therapeutic response. For triple-negative breast cancers treated with neoadjuvant immune-checkpoint blockade, distinct differences were found between responders and non-responders when analyzing the phenotypes, activation states and spatial positions of cells in the TME (Wang et al., 2023).

Approaches to spatial biomarker discovery like cellular compositions within a predetermined radius around cancer cells or manually specified cell-cell distance measures have provided important insights, but each requires assumptions about which cell populations or interactions are relevant. While these approaches are readily interpretable, they may overlook complex patterns involving either several phenotypes simultaneously or unexpected phenotypes. Graph neural networks can preserve detailed TME structures and have identified outcome-associated spatial patterns, but their complexity may be difficult to constrain in small clinical cohorts (Wu et al., 2022). Therefore, a representation that summarizes the spatial composition surrounding individual cancer cells while remaining computationally efficient could therefore provide a useful compromise between spatial detail and model complexity.

In this publication, we present a weakly supervised spatial approach to learn TME structures associated with treatment response. In our implementation, this approach was applied on ER+ breast cancer core needle biopsies taken prior to treatment to find spatial structures important for response to neoadjuvant chemotherapy with bevacizumab, as well as to classify the response of samples in a held-out test set.

Methods

Patient cohort

The data for this study was obtained from the NeoAva clinical trial (NCT00773695) which explored the use of the VEGF inhibitor bevacizumab in a neoadjuvant setting. A total of 132 triple negative or ER⁺/HER2⁻ breast cancer patients with locally advanced breast cancer were included in this study. Enrolled patients were randomized 1:1 and received either standard chemotherapy consisting of four cycles with 5-fluorouracil, epirubicin and cyclophosphamide every three weeks for 12 weeks followed by docetaxel every three weeks or weekly paclitaxel for 12 weeks, or standard chemotherapy with the addition of bevacizumab. Core needle biopsies of breast tumor tissues were taken during screening prior to treatment, at 12 weeks on treatment, and at surgery at 25 weeks. The primary endpoint of NeoAva was pathological complete response (pCR) measured at time of surgery.

Cyclic immunofluorescence imaging

For the development of the presented method, the screening biopsies of 13 ER⁺ patients in the bevacizumab arm, six responders and seven non-responders, were selected at random for cyclic immunofluorescence (CyclIF) imaging. A complete overview of this process can be found in the publication of Lin et.al (Lin et al., 2015). In brief, 5 µm sections of FFPE tissue samples were first imaged without fluorescent stain to determine auto-fluorescence levels followed by cycles stained with four fluorescently labeled antibodies and DAPI. Between cycles, the fluorescence molecules were quenched using a solution of 3% peroxide and 20 mM NaOH in PBS. All imaging was performed at 10X magnification using the Axioscan Z1 fluorescence slide scanner (Zeiss). A complete overview of the staining cycles and antibody targets is shown in Supplementary Table 1. For CD20 and CD11b, the staining was found to be non-specific following imaging, resulting in the exclusion of these markers from the data set.

Image pre-processing and segmentation

Image pre-processing and segmentation was performed on the Cancer Galaxy server at cancer.usegalaxy.org using the MCMICRO pipeline (Schapiro et al., 2022). Shading correction of individual image tiles and stitching of tiles and staining cycles were performed using BaSiC and ASHLAR respectively (Muhlich et al., 2022; Peng et al., 2017) For cell segmentation, the Mesmer software tool was used (Greenwald et al., 2021). Here, the DAPI stain of the first and last cycle was used as the nucleus marker while cytokeratins, e-cadherin and CD45 served as membrane markers. To extract the single cell protein expressions from the segmented cells, we used MCQUANT, which returned single cell data

sets with the log_{1p} transformed signal-to-background ratio for all markers, each cell's position in the image and a unique cell id (Schapiro et al., 2022).

Phenotyping

Phenotyping was performed using hierarchical gating of selected protein markers. The selected markers, the inferred cell phenotype, and gating sequence are shown in Table 1. Any cells that were not assigned a phenotype during this process were marked as “unknown”. Thresholds for each marker were set manually based on inspection of the marker specific histograms for each sample and the fluorescent images. As quality control, each phenotyped data set was inspected visually using Vitessce to confirm validity of the phenotyping (Keller et al., 2024). Following phenotyping, the single cell data sets were expanded with the identified phenotype for each cell. In total, nine different phenotypes were identified, cancer cells, stromal cells, endothelial cells, dendritic cells, macrophages, CD4 T-cells, CD8 T-cells regulatory T-cells and remaining immune cells. Cells classified as “unknown” were removed from the data set.

Definition of section boundaries and defect areas

To exclude cells detected outside of the biopsy section or in defect areas, we marked valid areas in FIJI (ver. 2.16.0/1.54p, (Schindelin et al., 2012)). First, the border of the biopsy section was added as a region of interest (ROI) by inspecting the DAPI channel of the first four CyclF cycles. By comparing the DAPI channels of all cycles, defect areas where the biopsy section was damaged between staining cycles were identified, traced out, and added as ROIs. Following inspection of all cycles, the ROIs of all defect areas were combined and subtracted from the total biopsy section resulting in a ROI representing the valid in-section area.

To determine each cell's distance to the section boundary or a defect area, a distance map storing the distance from each pixel to the nearest border of the valid in-section ROI as the pixel value was calculated using the distance map function of FIJI. Using this distance map and the pixel position of each cell, cells positioned outside the biopsy section or in defect areas were removed from the single cell data set. Additionally, each cell's distance to the nearest border was calculated.

Radial projection of cancer cell neighborhoods

Cancer cell neighborhoods (NHs) were defined as the collection of cells surrounding a central cancer cell within a given radius. The optimal NH radius for response prediction was explored during cross validation. The largest explored NH radius was chosen to be 200 μm

based on the approximate range of cell-to-cell communications found in earlier research (Francis & Palsson, 1997; Oyler-Yaniv et al., 2017). An example NH is shown in Figure 1c.

To create NH datasets, cancer cells were identified in each sample. Cancer cells within 200 μm of a biopsy section boundary or defect area were excluded to avoid partial NHs. For each remaining cancer cell, neighboring cells within the chosen NH radius were identified and their radial distance to the central cancer cell calculated. Based on these radial distances, histograms were calculated for each of the nine identified phenotypes with a bin size of 10 μm . To account for the increased area of more distant bins when compared to closer bins, the counts in each histogram bin were divided by the bin area, resulting in radial density distributions.

Following these calculations, each NH data point consisted of a collection of nine radial density distributions, one distribution for each phenotype, representing the local cellular configurations (Figure 1d). We chose to split these data points into a distribution part and a magnitude part to optimize the neural network for each of these information types (Figure 1e). The distribution part was represented as a matrix containing the radial distribution of each phenotype normalized to a phenotype-wise sum of one. For cases where no cells of a given phenotype were present, the respective distribution was set to a uniform distribution, also with a radial sum of one. The magnitude information was stored in a separate vector, where for each phenotype, the original phenotype-wise sum was stored.

To compensate for large differences in the prevalence of different phenotypes (Figure 1a), we also normalized the magnitude vectors across each phenotype. This normalization was performed using a Yeo-Johnson power transform without standardization implemented in scikit learn (Pedregosa et al., 2011; Yeo, 2000). To compensate for outliers with high magnitude vectors, the magnitude vectors were additionally divided by the 99th percentile for each phenotype. Both the lambdas of the power transform and 99th percentiles for each phenotype were calculated solely on training data and re-used to transform the validation and testing data sets.

Model training

Model development and training were performed using Python 3.12.12 and TensorFlow 2.20.0 with the TensorFlow Keras API version 3.13.2 on a Linux workstation running Ubuntu 24.04.4 LTS. GPU acceleration was provided by an NVIDIA GeForce RTX 3070 with 8 GB memory using NVIDIA driver 590.48.01 with CUDA 12.5.1 and cuDNN 9.

Prior to model training, a test set was reserved containing two responders and two non-responders, with the total NH count of both responders and non-responders being approximately 20% of the total NH count in their respective groups. Within these constraints,

the test set was chosen at random. The remaining nine samples, five responders and four non-responders were used as a training / validation set for cross validation. We performed cross validation with a leave-two-out strategy. For each fold, one responder and one non-responder were selected for the validation set. We created folds for every possible responder and non-responder combination, resulting in a total of 20 folds.

The batches used for model training and validation were created by a custom generator. Prior to batch generation, the order of NH datapoints in each sample was randomized. Each batch was divided into bags of NH data points, with each bag only containing data points from a single biological sample (Figure 2a). As many bags as possible were created for each sample with residual data points unable to fill a complete bag being discarded. Weights were calculated to ensure equal total contribution across response groups as well as samples during training and validation. For training, the generator was initialized with a random seed and new bags generated after each epoch. During validation, the generator was initialized with a fixed seed across all folds and hyperparameter combinations and iterated over the complete validation set three times to ensure that single NH datapoints were present in multiple bag configurations.

During cross validation, three different model architectures were tested, termed mean-vote model, vote-attention model, and bag-embedding model. All three models were a combination of an auto encoder designed to project a NH datapoint to a latent layer with a weakly supervised multiple instance learning (MIL) module designed to predict an outcome based on the latent representation of the data points. Both the auto encoder and MIL module were trained simultaneously. A schematic of the three different model architectures is given in Figure 2. The mean-vote model assigned each neighborhood an instance-level response score and used the average score across sampled neighborhoods as the bag-level response prediction. The vote-attention model decomposed each neighborhood into a signed response vote and an instance importance weight, and aggregated neighborhoods by a normalized weighted average of their votes. The bag-embedding attention model used gated attention to aggregate latent neighborhood representations into a single bag-level embedding, which was then classified as responder-like or non-responder-like.

The hyperparameters investigated during cross validation were the model architecture, MIL bag size, NH radial size, size of the latent space, L2 loss weight, dropout, initial learning rate, number of kernels in convolutional layers, and weight of the reconstruction losses. Initial coarse cross validation focused on finding the optimal model type across varying bag sizes, number of NH bins, latent sizes and dropouts. Following coarse cross validation, the hyperparameters for the best performing model architecture were further optimized based on successive cross validation runs.

For training, the loss was a weighted sum of L2 normalization loss on all kernel weights, a custom Wasserstein distance loss on the reconstructed distribution matrix, mean squared error loss on the reconstructed magnitude vector, and binary cross entropy loss on the predicted response for each bag. Additionally, a sample wise logistic ranking loss was calculated based on the response predictions of the validation set. The sample wise logistic ranking loss was calculated as shown below:

$$\frac{1}{|R||N|} \sum_{r \in R} \sum_{n \in N} \log(1 + e^{-(z_r - z_n)})$$

Where R is the set of all responders, N is the set of all non-responders and z is the average prediction across all bags.

This loss was used during model training for early stopping and the dynamic reduction of learning rate on improvement plateaus. Additionally, we used this loss to choose the best performing hyperparameters.

The best performing hyperparameters following cross validation are shown in Table 3. For the final model, 12 models, each with their own random seed for kernel initialization and training set generation, were trained on all nine samples of the training / validation dataset. To get a single prediction from this ensemble, the average prediction across all 12 models was calculated.

Results

Defining cancer cell neighborhoods

Screening core needle biopsies from ER+ breast cancer were classified based on residual cancer burden (RCB) at surgery (n=13). Samples were labeled as responders (RCB0/1) or non-responders (RCB2/3), resulting in seven responders and six non-responders. Following segmentation and phenotyping, approximately 7×10^5 cells with identified phenotypes were found across all core needle biopsies (Figure 1a). For each sample, cancer cell neighborhoods (NHs) were constructed as described in the methods section, with an illustration of this process shown in Figure 1b – e. In brief, for each cancer cell, all cells within a given radius were included in its NH. For each phenotype, a radial density distribution was then calculated from the central cancer cell to the NH edge, and for model training represented as a distribution matrix normalized to a phenotype-wise sum of one, and a magnitude vector, representing the absolute magnitude for each phenotype prior to normalization.

Out of the 13 samples, two responders and two non-responders were held out at random for testing of the final model, with the constraint that the total number of NHs in the held-out data sets equaled approximately 20% of the total NHs found in all responders and non-responders (Figure 1f).

Multiple-instance learning model architectures for response prediction

Since the response labels are only available on the sample-level and not at the NH-level, multiple instance learning (MIL) was utilized to train our models. To prepare the data sets for this training method, NH data points from single samples were grouped into bags and inherited the response label of their sample (Figure 2a). For training and inference, multiple bags of NHs were combined to form batches.

Three different model architectures were explored. All three models share an autoencoder module architecture for the projection of the NH data points to a latent representation (Figure 2b). The three different MIL module architectures differed in how the single NH data points were interpreted for bag level prediction, but all resulted in a score between 0 and 1 for non-responders and responders respectively. (i) The mean vote model was designed to predict the bag label by first predicting a response score for each NH datapoint followed by mean pooling to determine a bag label. (ii) The attention vote model calculated two scores for each NH datapoint, a “vote” between -1 and 1 to represent non-response and response respectively, and an attention score between 0 and 1 to represent the importance of that NH datapoint. To calculate a bag prediction, the weighted average was calculated across all NH datapoints within the bag, and the results rescaled to between 0 and 1. (iii) The bag embedding model calculated a bag-level embedding in the latent space by first calculating an attention score for each NH data point and combining this with the original latent NH vector. The combined bag embedding was passed to a prediction head to compute a bag prediction.

While approximately 2×10^5 NH data points were generated across all data sets, these were based on 13 biological samples. To avoid inaccurate metrics due to non-independent data points, we chose to evaluate models based on a sample-wise logistic ranking metric (Figure 2c), instead of bag-wise metrics. In brief, the bag-wise response predictions were averaged for each sample and converted to a logit representation. For each responder and non-responder combination, softplus was applied on the difference between these averages, resulting in a low score for correct separation, a high score for incorrect separation, and a score of $\sim \ln(2)$ for no separation.

Cross validation

Cross-validation was performed in four runs to determine the optimal hyperparameter configuration. Folds were generated by calculating each possible combination of one responder and one non-responder in the cross-validation data set, resulting in a total of 20 folds. A complete overview of tested hyperparameters in each run is shown in Table 2. For the first run, the main goal was to identify the optimal model architecture. Here, the (iii) bag-embedding model was found to perform the best based on the logistic ranking loss (Figure 3a). Further cross-validation optimized the hyperparameters for this model architecture (Figure 3b and c). The training stability across seeds was investigated for the two best performing models. Here, the model with four and eight kernels achieved a similar median logistic ranking loss of 0.18 (IQR 0.15 – 0.21) and 0.20 (IQR 0.18 – 0.26) respectively across 12 different seeds. For the final model, we selected the best performing hyperparameters shown in Table 3.

While the models were stable across random seeds during cross validation, performance exhibited substantial variation across validation folds. When investigating the results of the final model configuration across 12 different seeds, folds containing samples S4, S5 and S7 in the validation set were found to result in higher logistic ranking loss while the combinations of S4 and S6, S5 and S7, and S3 and S8 in the validation set resulted in a mean logistic ranking loss close to $\ln(2)$ indicating that the models assigned similar response predictions to both samples in these pairs (Figure 3e).

Ensemble performance on held-out test set

A predictor ensemble was created by training 12 models using the best performing hyperparameters (Table 3) with different seeds on the entire cross-validation data set. To evaluate the performance of this ensemble, we predicted the response of the four samples in the held-out testing set (Figure 4a). The ensemble means correctly ranked all responders above the non-responders. While both responders received a response score close to their true response label of 1, the non-responders received average scores of 0.43 and 0.70, with non-response being defined as a score of 0. Additionally, a higher variance across ensemble sub-models was observed for non-responder samples when compared to responder samples. The ensemble scored high in pair-wise sample level AUC and low for logistic ranking loss, confirming good separation between positive and negative samples (Figure 4b). Patient-level BCE was used to evaluate classification performance. Here, the ensemble scored an average of 0.45, reflecting the high scores assigned to non-responders.

While the ensemble was trained on bags of NH data points, single data points were further investigated. When evaluating single NH data points without bagging, the score distributions

of the testing samples show a trend towards one and zero for responders and non-responders respectively Figure 4c. For the samples included in the training set, in non-responders, the score distributions were also found to be skewed towards zero, while in responders, scores were more spread across the entire range from zero to one, with one responder sample receiving a median and mean score of under 0.5.

We used symmetric thresholds of 0.25 and 0.75 on the 0–1 prediction scale. Scores in the upper quarter of the scale (>0.75) were interpreted as responder-like, scores in the lower quarter of the scale (<0.25) as non-responder-like, and scores in the central range as indeterminate. To investigate the prevalence of responder-like NHs in each sample, we calculated the fraction of NHs classified as responder-like among all NHs in that sample (Figure 4d). In the training set, we found average fractions of 0.4 and 0.1 in responders and non-responders respectively, while in the testing set, on average a fraction of 0.7 and 0.2 of NHs had responder-like character in responders and non-responders respectively. All responders scored higher than all non-responders, except for sample S3.

Biological characterization of response-like NHs

To investigate the biological composition of NHs predicted to be responder-like by the prediction model, we first investigated the average cell phenotype composition within the high scoring NHs and compared them to NHs scoring below 0.25 in the same sample. We found a significantly higher sample-wise average of all immune cells in high scoring NHs when compared to low-scoring NHs (Figure 5a).

When looking at the fraction of high- and low-scoring NHs containing at least one of the immune cells within their radius, we also found a significantly increased likelihood of presence in high- scoring NHs when compared to low-scoring NHs (Figure 5b). Presence of macrophages and residual immune cells (CD45) were found to be especially common in high-scoring NHs.

To further investigate the degree of co-location between the central cancer cells and the neighboring immune cells, we calculated the average distance between the central cancer cell and the closest cell of the different immune cells (Figure 5c). For all immune cells, this average minimum distance was smaller in high-scoring NHs when compared to low-scoring NHs. On average, the closest cell types were found to be residual CD45 positive immune cells and macrophages.

Spatial heterogeneity of response-like scores

To demonstrate how the NH responder-like scores were distributed in the tissue samples, these were projected back onto tissue coordinates to create spatial heatmaps (Figure 5).

NH-scores were found to be spatially structured, forming distinct areas of high and low responder-like scores in all samples. The NH responder-like scores showed distinct sample-level distributions in both the training and test cohorts. Responder biopsies generally exhibited higher scores across all NHs, although they also contained localized regions with low responder-like scores. Conversely, non-responder biopsies were dominated by low-scoring NHs but contained discrete patches of responder-like areas.

Earlier analyses showed a trend of increased immune presence in high-scoring NHs when compared to low-scoring NHs (Figure 5). When analyzing the spatial structure of high and low scoring areas in our samples, however, we found instances where this general trend was not followed. A high-scoring NH with low immune presence and a low-scoring NH with high immune presence are shown in Figure 6 b and c respectively.

Discussion

In this study, we presented a novel approach tying spatial patterns around cancer cells to treatment response predictions. Compared to direct spatial metrics, such as the average minimum distance between cell phenotypes or other co-location measurements, this approach can potentially capture complex interactions between multiple phenotypes without any prior assumptions besides the assignment of phenotypes based on underlying marker expressions.

Before model training, we observed variability in the cell compositions and cell count in our samples. While phenotype fractions were broadly similar across samples, sample ST1 showed a large deviation in the cancer cell fraction when compared to other samples. The number of NHs obtained from each sample also greatly varied. For the largest sample (S8) we identified almost 4×10^4 NHs, while the smallest sample (S4) contained only 2300. To compensate for this imbalance, we implemented weighting of the training and validation metrics for each sample to ensure equal impact, however a smaller sample size may still lead to less granular features learned from these samples. When looking at the difficulty matrix in Figure 3e, we identified some samples for which the models consistently performed poorly across seeds. The combinations of samples: S4 and S6, S5 and S7, and S3 and S8 in the validation sets resulted in poor model performance, assigning similar predictions to both responders and non-responders. We were unable to find a consistent explanation for all discrepancies. When looking at the sample compositions and sizes, shown in Figure 1a and f respectively, the relatively small sizes of samples S4 and S7, as well as the marginally low fractions of cancer cells in S4, S5 and S7 could explain the poor performance on these folds. An additional factor could be the low count of biological samples when compared to the heterogeneity of cancer. If a sample contains response- or

non-response-associated spatial features that are not found in other samples of the training set, placing this sample in the validation set would leave the model unable to learn the required features for correct response prediction. Excluding the poor performing folds, cross validation indicated stable learning across different seeds for the top-performing hyperparameters (Figure 3b).

Using radial projections to generate NH data points greatly simplified the data structure by resulting in a consistent number of elements for each NH regardless of cell count and distribution around the central cancer cells. This simplification, however, came at the expense of losing accurate cell-to-cell distances between cells within a cancer cell's NH, and thereby information on potential cell interactions. While the model in its presented form performed satisfactorily, we believe that incorporating the whole 2D spatial arrangement in a NH data point could further improve the predictive power of the model, albeit potentially requiring a more complex model architecture and larger training sets.

While training performance across seeds was found to be stable, we chose to construct the final prediction model as an ensemble of 12 prediction models trained on different seeds to reduce the risk of poor initialization weights. This further enabled the calculation of variance between sub-models, potentially identifying uncertain predictions. When evaluating the final ensemble on a held-out testing set, we observed good ranking, with both responders receiving a response prediction above both non-responders (Figure 4a). Non-responders in the test set were found to have larger uncertainties in their predictions and were generally placed further from their true label when compared to responders. An ensemble BCE of 0.45 confirms a lower performance in classification compared to ranking (Figure 4b). While BCE was used during training of the model, the use of a ranking focused metric for hyperparameter selection and early stopping could explain this characteristic. To improve this performance, training using a larger data set, an additional threshold calibration step, or selection with a classification focused metric such as sample BCE could be used to improve this performance.

We also explored the use of our predictive model on single NH data points instead of on bags. While the model may also produce results for single NHs, care must be taken in the interpretation. The bag-embedding model chosen was trained to predict response based on a latent feature vector representing a combination of 100 NHs. Evaluating a single NH latent vector instead could indicate how similar this feature vector is to a bag embedding of a responder, but not necessarily whether this NH induces response directly. Hence, when describing scores assigned to single NHs, the term responder-like score instead of response score was used. The other explored model architectures more directly assign a response score to a single NH before pooling the scores to determine a bag label (Figure 2b). These

models were, however, not selected for the final ensemble due to inferior performance on a sample level.

The general characterization of high-scoring NHs indicated that the model captured immune-rich local tumor microenvironments. Responder-like NHs contained higher densities of immune cells, and immune cells were more frequently located close to the NH-defining cancer cell (Figure 5). This is consistent with previous studies showing that tumor-infiltrating lymphocytes (TILs) are associated with response to neoadjuvant chemotherapy and prognosis in breast cancer (Denkert et al., 2018) (Denkert et al., 2010). Notably, macrophages were among the most enriched and proximal immune phenotypes in high-scoring NHs. Given the context-dependent roles of macrophages in chemotherapy response and clinical outcomes (Azimzade et al., 2026), this finding should be interpreted as hypothesis-generating and will require validation in larger cohorts and ideally with additional markers resolving macrophage functional states. Our findings are consistent with recent spatial proteomics work in melanoma where machine-learning models integrating cell composition and spatial features could identify responder-associated tissue regions, whereas single features were insufficient (Pybus et al., 2026). In contrast to their fixed 1 mm² tile-based approach, our model used cancer-cell-centered neighborhoods, potentially capturing more relevant information for each cancer cell and yielding predictions with better spatial resolution.

While the aggregated spatial trends of responder-like NHs agree with the earlier mentioned studies, closer investigation of the spatial composition of high- and low-scoring NHs revealed that these trends were not always driving the prediction model. Some high-scoring areas of samples were found to have a low immune presence, and low-scoring areas could also contain a large number of immune cells (Figure 6 b and c). While this interpretation must be made cautiously, individual neighborhood-level scores may reflect local differences in treatment response, illustrating the potential of this approach to identify tumor microenvironment structures that warrant deeper biological investigation.

When exploring the spatial distribution of NH-level responder-like scores, we noticed substantial heterogeneity within samples. While both responders and non-responders were found to predominantly feature NHs with scores agreeing with their respective sample response, we also found areas with contradicting responder-like scores in each sample (Figure 6a). When interpreting the responder-like scores to correlate with local treatment response, this suggests that non-responder samples may still contain localized regions with response-associated microenvironmental structures, but that these regions are not sufficiently abundant to drive a meaningful overall response. Conversely, responder

samples contained patches of non-responder-like NHs, which may represent residual resistant regions that could potentially contribute to recurrence.

Limitations

The main limitation of this study is that despite including a large number of NHs, the overall cohort size was relatively small. The number of NHs extracted was sufficient for stable model training, but patient or biopsy specific TME structures might still be misinterpreted as response specific structures due to the limited number of tissue samples. While validation was performed on held-out samples to investigate the model's generalizability, the validation set contained just four samples, and the results should therefore be interpreted with care.

Conclusions

In this study, we showed that weakly supervised multiple-instance learning can be combined with radial representations of cancer-cell neighborhoods to identify spatial TME patterns associated with treatment response in breast cancer core needle biopsies. Our approach provided patient-level separation in cross-validation and ranked held-out responders above non-responders, supporting the presence of response-associated spatial information in pretreatment tissue. Mapping model-derived responder-like scores back onto tissue coordinates revealed areas deemed to be important for treatment response, and potential candidates for future investigation.

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